

INTERFACIAL ADHESION BETWEEN GLASS FIBERS AND ACRYLIC-BASED MATRICES AS STUDIED BY MICROMECHANICAL TESTING

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ABSTRACT

The quality of adhesion between a polymer matrix and reinforcing fibers, which may be affected by the composite processing parameters, strongly conditions the performances of the final part and so has to be evaluated. For this purpose, PMMA/glass fiber (GF) model specimens were prepared by in-situ polymerizing a MMA-based reactive mixture onto a single glass filament. Two micromechanical tests on single filament composites have been used to evaluate the interfacial adhesion: the single fiber fragmentation test and the microbond test. Fibers sizing nature and sample processing conditions have been varied to study the influence of these parameters on fiber/matrix interface. Interfacial shear strength (IFSS) values were evaluated according to well-known theoretical models and compared with values obtained on thermosets glass/epoxy reference samples. PMMA/GF interfacial adhesions which have been evaluated by fragmentation test compete with the one measured on epoxy system. In contrast, a much better adhesion was observed in the epoxy systems for microdroplet specimens. The sizing nature does not impact significantly the PMMA/GF adhesion quality. On the contrary, the latter strongly depends on the sample preparation conditions (monomer evaporation...) and so it can be reasonably anticipated that the composite processing conditions will significantly impact the interface quality.

1 INTRODUCTION

Nowadays, fiber-reinforced composites are widely used in various industrial sectors as aerospace, automotive, public utility or sports [1]. The loss of weight for equivalent properties in comparison with metallic alloys makes them attractive. Historically, these materials were designed using thermosets (TS) as it is well known that the latter offer better mechanical properties and durability than thermoplastics (TP). However, new environmental issues and especially a growing need for recyclability motivate efforts to develop solutions involving TP matrices [1]. TP-based composites are commonly processed by hot-pressing of pre-impregnated reinforcing plies. But TP usually exhibit high viscosity in the molten state and as a consequence the fiber impregnation is not always satisfying [2].

Thus efforts are paid to develop more reliable and cost-effective processing strategies for these materials. In this framework, a reactive process like Resin Transfer Molding (RTM) constitutes an appealing approach since it is based on a low-pressure injection of a monomer into a mold containing a dry preform. RTM is usually involved in TS-based composites processing but can be extended to TP composites providing that the latter can be synthesized from low viscosity monomers (< 1 Pa.s). If compared with hot-pressing, RTM is expected to yield composites with better interfacial adhesion since the viscosity of the impregnating resin is initially very low.

Poly (methyl methacrylate) (PMMA) is a possible candidate for RTM processing since it can be obtained from MMA by radical polymerization using a thermal initiator [3]. Actually radical polymerization can take place at moderate temperature, does not require any inert environment and processing cycle can be adjusted by a careful choice of catalysts and inhibitors.

The aim of our work is to investigate the quality of interface generated by a radical polymerization of a low-viscosity acrylic resin onto a glass fiber in order to model the impregnation steps occurring during a RTM process. To our knowledge, TP/GF interfaces generated by a reactive approach have not often been studied so far. For such a purpose, micromechanical tests have been performed in order to quantify the acrylic/glass adhesion. First, MMA radical polymerization conditions (formulations, temperature...) have been optimized to process reliable micro-droplets and fragmentation specimens. Then micromechanical tests have been carried out and resulting data were compared to previous work dealing with both TS and TP-based systems.

2 INTERFACIAL SHEAR STRENGTH (IFSS) MEASUREMENT BY MICRO-MECHANICAL TESTING

2.1 The single fiber fragmentation test

This test was first developed by Kelly and Tyson [4]. It consists in inserting a single filament into a matrix tensile specimen. During sample solicitation, the reinforcing fiber which is supposed to own a shorter elongation at break than the matrix (usually 3 to 4 times shorter) breaks into multiples fragments until a phenomenon called saturation is reached. The obtained fragment length distribution is related to the interface quality.

The two classical and well-known unidimensional stress-based approaches are Cox's theory and Kelly's theory. Cox [5] makes the hypothesis that the matrix and the fiber are well bonded, so the resulting effort at the interface should come from the difference of strain between a fragmentation specimen and a matrix sample alone. It suggests an elastic stress transfer during the fragmentation process. In contrast, Kelly [4] assumes that the interface between both components is not bonded implying a total plastic behaviour of the matrix. The shear strength is consequently constant along the fragment length. The maximal final fragmentation length is referred as the critical length " l_c " and is a function of the interfacial shear strength (IFSS):

$$\bar{\tau} = \frac{r_f}{l_c} \cdot \sigma_{l_c} \quad (1)$$

Where r_f is the radius of the filament and σ_{l_c} its failure strength at l_c . The critical length can be determined from the average fragment length:

$$l_c = \frac{4}{3} \cdot \bar{l} \quad (2)$$

From these two models, Pigott first discussed of a partially elastic model inspired by both approaches [6]. Lacroix & al. established that the partially elastic model was the most realistic for fiber reinforced polymer and proved that Kelly's model is unable to distinguish between interfacial bond strength and frictional shear strength [7]. This was confirmed by Zhandharov who mentioned that Kelly's formula, which is not based on the concept of local debonding, is not relevant to describe interfacial bonding [8].

It has also to be pointed out that a unidimensional load transfer is assumed. In fact the stress field is axisymmetric and the basic models do not take into account the thermal residual and the Poisson radial effort. Pigott attempted to incorporate the latter into general equations [9].

Other criterions have since been developed in order to model and describe more accurately the mechanisms occurring during the fragmentation like modified axisymmetric stress-based, energy-based or finite element approaches but generally these concepts are more elaborated and require specific or advanced mathematical tools to be solved [10]. Despite of their limitations, it seems that the Kelly's and Cox's approximations remain quite relevant to discuss interfacial issues from a chemical-physic point of view but obtained values have to be discussed very carefully. Once the fragmentation test has been performed, it is also necessary to check if the sample failure mode is consistent with either Kelly or Cox theoretical hypotheses.

2.2 Microbond test

Miller first proposed this test as an alternative to the pull-out test [11]. It consists in depositing a droplet of monomer onto a stretched single filament. A curing cycle then allows for monomer polymerization. Droplet volume is supposed to be sufficiently low so that the droplet is not impacted by gravity. The fiber specimen is then fixed onto a paper support, installed in a tensile machine and the droplet debonded by two razor blades. Debonded force is measured and put in relation with embedded length.

As for the fragmentation, there are several approaches of the microdebonding which depends on the failure mode at the interface and consequently on the matrix states when failure occurs [12]. Numerous stress-based and energy-based models are described in the literature, computing several physical parameters of both polymer matrix and reinforcing fiber as well as sample geometry. The most relevant of them were discussed by Zinck and al. with glass/epoxy specimens [13].

The most common method allowing to quantify the interfacial adhesion stays the average IFFS given by:

$$\bar{\tau} = \frac{F_d}{\pi d_f l_e} \quad (3)$$

As suggest with Kelly's model [4], a constant shear strength is assumed along the embedded length. Although the veracity and the accuracy of this method have been controverted [13], it can be considered as a straightforward and reliable method.

2.3 Fiber mechanical properties at short gauge length

Glass fibers are brittle materials. Every single filament carries an important number of flaws as the result of elaboration, transport and storage. Weibull described an approach based on the weakest-link theory implying that in a longer fiber, there was a higher probability to find an important flaw leading to its breaking and so the fiber strength should decrease with its length [14]. The two-parameter Weibull distribution is given by:

$$P(\sigma) = 1 - e^{-l\left(\frac{\sigma}{\sigma_o}\right)^m} \quad (4)$$

Where $P(\sigma)$ is the cumulative probability of failure of a reinforcing fiber of length l at applied stress σ , and m and σ_o are respectively the shape and the scale parameter of the Weibull distribution.

Extrapolation of fiber strength at short gauge length is now made on the assumption that scale and shape parameters are invariant for a population of brittle materials, thus correlating the main failure strength $\bar{\sigma}_1$ and $\bar{\sigma}_2$ of a same filament at respective length l_1 and l_2 :

$$\bar{\sigma}_2 = \bar{\sigma}_1 \cdot \left(\frac{l_1}{l_2}\right)^{1/m} \quad (5)$$

Experimentally, several authors have proven that m and σ_o are not material constants and that eq. (5)-based extrapolations were far from experimental observation [15]. Asloun and al. discussed about another method while working on carbon fibers [16]. The theoretical mean failure strength of a Weibull distribution can be written as:

$$\bar{\sigma} = \frac{\sigma_o}{l_o^{1/m}} \cdot \Gamma\left(\frac{m+1}{m}\right) \quad (6)$$

Taking the log of the last equation, a linear relationship is obtained between gauge length and mean failure strength:

$$\ln(\sigma) = -\frac{1}{m} \cdot \ln(l_o) + \ln\left[\sigma_o \cdot \Gamma\left(\frac{m+1}{m}\right)\right] \quad (7)$$

This last method has proven to be a good estimator of glass fiber strength at short gauge length [17].

3 EXPERIMENTAL SECTION

3.1 Materials

Two types of reinforcing E-glass fibers of identical physical properties but different sizing were characterized: one is modified with a generic multi-compatible sizing (MSF) and the other with a specific acrylic-compatible sizing (ASF). Filament diameters were statistically determined by optical microscopy upon measuring 72 specimens from both batches. Size and distribution are shown below (Fig. 1). Average diameter ($d_f = 17.9 \pm 1.2 \mu\text{m}$) will be used for further calculation.

Figure 1: Distribution of fiber diameter

In order to evaluate the fiber strength, 5 lots of different gauge length (5, 10, 20, 35, 50mm) of 30 to 40 samples were characterized for each sizing with a MTS 2/m testing machine and a 10N sensor. Strain speed was 0.5mm/min. Evolution of mean strength failure with gauge length fitted with eq. (7) is available below with parameters of the linear regression (Fig. 2).

Treatment	$\ln(\sigma) = a \ln(l_0) + b$
MSF	$\ln(\sigma) = -0.15 \ln(l_0) + 1.1$
ASF	$\ln(\sigma) = -0.084 \ln(l_0) + 0.97$

Figure 2: Fibers mean failure strength versus gauge length for 2 different sizings

One can wonder why two physically identical populations of glass fiber were studied separately. Zinck and al. showed the possible regenerating impact of sizing on mechanical properties [18]. Since two different sizing are considered, failure strength could change, as indeed observed on our own results.

Acrylic matrices were obtained by radical polymerisation of an Elium resin (Arkema) (viscosity of 300cP) activated by a thermal initiator, benzoyl peroxide (BPO), and amine-based catalyst. As the resulting TP matrix is also depending on the initiator/catalyst quantities and ratio, a brief study was made to evaluate the influence of the formulation content on molar mass distribution and consequently tensile strength properties. 5 plates of 2mm thick were cured until vitrification at room temperature and post-cured at 80°C for 1h. Quantities of BPO have been varied between 0.37 and 1.12 phr while keeping an equimolar BPO/catalyst ratio. Molar mass distribution were measured by GPC in THF with 3 Shimadzu Stryragel HR 5E columns in series (35°C, 1ml/min with Shimadzu UFLC pump) and RID-10A detection with PMMA conventional calibration. Results are given in Fig. 3 and Table 1.

Figure 3: Matrix molar mass distribution for different reactive formulations

Sample	–	L-0.50	L-0.75	L-1.00	L-1.25	L-1.50
<i>phr BPO</i>	–	0.37	0.56	0.76	0.93	1.12
<i>molar ratio (initiator/catalyst)</i>	–	1.1	1.1	0.9	1.0	1.0
<i>Mw</i>	[kg/mol]	596	517	337	248	218
<i>IP</i>	–	6.8	7.4	6.0	5.6	5.2

Table 1: Matrix molar masses weight and polydispersity index for different formulations and after post-curing at 80°C

H2 specimens were machined with a “Charly 4U” (carbide metal FDCI-AC Φ3m (Diamix), rotation speed 8000r/min, advance speed 4mm/s) and tested with a MTS 2/m testing machine and a 10kN sensor at 0.5mm/min in order to measure Young modulus and ultimate strain (Fig. 4). Optical extensometer was used to measure true elongation strain. For each formulation, 7 to 12 specimens were tested. Results show average values and standard deviation

Figure 4: Matrix Young modulus and strain at break versus BPO content

Despite of the variation observed in molar mass distribution, the mechanical properties are not significantly affected by the formulation composition. Further microcomposite specimens will be processed from L-1.00 formulation.

3.2 Single fiber composite elaboration, mechanical testing and observations

In order to discuss single fiber fragmentation results, it is necessary that each specimen reaches the saturation. If the matrix breaks too soon, the fragment distribution is associated with a stationary state and nothing can be deduced from it. The essential prerequisite is that the ultimate matrix strain is at least 3 to 4 times higher than the fiber elongation at break. In the case of glass filament, values between 3 and 4% are mentioned for elongation at break which means that the matrix must endure more than 10% of strain before breaking. It is not the case for PMMA at room temperature but at 50°C, an elongation at

break larger than 20% is measured. It means that fragmentation tests on PMMA are relevant when performed at 50°C

For manufacturing fragmentation samples, a comb of pre-strained single filaments was disposed between two 1mm joints. Then the reactive Elium-based formulation was poured into a 2mm-thick mold. For the formulation BPO quantity was fixed at 0.75 phr in the Elium resin and catalyst was added in equimolar ratio. After vitrification at room temperature, the samples of 2mm thick were then post-cured at 80°C for 1 hour. H2 specimens were processed around the embedded fibers with a milling machine “Charly 4U” (carbide metal FDCI-AC Φ 3m (Diamix), rotation speed 8000r/min, advance speed 4mm/s) and tested with a MTS 2/m testing machine and a 10kN sensor at 0.5mm/min at 50°C. Specimens were pre-heated before testing. Since samples were placed in a heating chamber, an extensometer cannot be used.

For manufacturing microdroplet samples, single glass filaments were pre-stressed and fixed onto a metallic support. Resin droplets were then dropped onto the fiber with a cobber thread ($\Phi=100\mu\text{m}$) and cured for 1h at 80°C followed by 2h at 150°C. For the reactive formulation BPO quantity was fixed at 0.75 phr in Elium resin and catalyst was added in equimolar ratio. In this case, 0.7 phr of paraffin wax was also added to prevent evaporation of MMA during curing. Fibers were cut and stuck onto a paper support. Embedded lengths were determined by optical microscopy. Droplets were finally debonded at 0.1mm/min by two razor blades in a MTS 2/m testing machine equipped with a 10N sensor. To monitor the test, a SVCam-ECO655 camera was used with a macrozoom objective (up to 0.4x0.3mm) so the stress-strain curve can be related to the failure mode and experimental values immediately be validated.

Reference samples were synthesized the same way with a conventional DGEBA epoxy system cured 1h at 80°C then 2h at 160°C. Debonding conditions were also identical.

All specimens were observed after testing with a Zeiss AxioScope.A1 link to an AxioCam ICc5 in bright field. Fragments were characterized with TL at x100 and x500 and droplet with RL at x500.

3.3 Kinetic of the fragmentation process

Figure 5: Kinetic of the fragmentation process vs strain-stress curves for ASF-based samples

The Kelly’s and Cox’s model assumptions impose to track the matrix state during the fragmentation process since it governs the interfacial behaviour. Among tracking methods, acoustic emission (AE) has been well studied and proved to be very efficient. In our case, it was not possible to use AE so the fragmentation kinetic was monitored by stopping the test at successive strain rates to follow the critical length evolution (Fig. 5). Near 15% of the machine strain, it seems that the samples reach the saturation but 20% has been chosen as threshold. Fragments appear between 7% and 8% of machine elongation. Strain-stress curves at these percentages show plastic behaviour. Kelly’s approach is theoretically justified.

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Average values and standard deviations obtained by fragmentation tests are presented in Tab. 2. Critical lengths vary with the type of sizing: the acrylic-compatible sizing leads to a lower average fragment length. However, using the Kelly formula, no conclusions can be made about a difference in the interfacial adhesion between both fibers since the latter do not own the same strength at break at short gauge length. Moreover, uncertainties are quite important for IFFS because of the two experimental values considered in Eq. (1). These values were determined using standard deviation for critical length and graphical uncertainties for fiber strength. The slight difference in the IFFS values is not significant if uncertainties are considered.

Sizing	–	ASF	MSF
l_c	[μm]	626 ± 44	755 ± 32
σ_{lc}	[GPa]	2.73 ± 0.20	3.19 ± 0.42
<i>IFFS</i>	[MPa]	39.3 ± 5.7	37.8 ± 6.6
l_c/d_f	–	35.0 ± 4.8	42.2 ± 4.6

Table 2: IFFS (measured by fragmentation) and critical aspect ratio of obtained fragments for both sizings

However, Kelly's hypothesis which assumes a constant stress along the embedded fiber seems inappropriate in our case. Indeed fragment observations for both samples show debonded areas near fiber ends implying that the interfacial stress field cannot be constant along the filament (Fig. 6). As a consequence IFFS values calculated from Kelly's formula can be overestimated [7].

Figure 6: Fragmented MSF fiber (left, x100) and decohesion near fragment breaking with ASF fiber (right, x500)

Mullin identified several modes of fracture for single-fiber composite during fragmentation experiments [20]. In our case it has been observed debonded areas at fragment end which usually reveal a weak interface and a disk-shaped matrix crack which usually accompanies a strong one. But no conclusions can be drawn from our specimens since both types of fracture have been observed simultaneously (Fig.6). It is also possible that these failure modes which are originally identified on brittle TS matrices do not apply to our TP system which suffers from a plastic deformation (close to T_w). It has also to be noted that PMMA and glass own very close refractive indexes which may compromise optical microscopy observations.

Comparing our IFFS values and critical aspect ratio with related systems from other works (sizing or fibers surface are optimized, but the polymer matrix is not modified with coupling agents) [21-25, 30-31], a strong interface is generated in our case (Tab. 3). Indeed values are very close to the ones

obtained for epoxy/glass systems and much higher than TP-based composites processed by hot pressing. However, it is important to have in mind that the temperature at which the test is carried out conditions the value of IFFS. It is established that critical length decreases when temperature reaches T_g of the matrix for TS specimens [21, 25, 31]. As a consequence comparison of adhesion level with different matrices should be discussed also considering their respective glass transition temperatures. Thus, fiber strengths used for calculating Kelly's IFFS are not always reported and/or could be much higher than our own experimental values. As extrapolation at short gauge length by Weibull statistic can lead to very scattered results, IFSS values have to be compared cautiously and critical aspect ratio (when available) will be preferred to discuss interfacial behavior.

References	ASF	MSF	[21] Di Benedetto	[22] Zhou	[25] Rao	[30] Zinck					
<i>Matrix</i>	–	<i>acrylic</i>	<i>epoxy</i>	<i>epoxy</i>	<i>epoxy</i>	<i>epoxy</i>					
<i>Fiber</i>	–	<i>E-glass</i>	<i>E-glass</i>	<i>E-glass</i>	<i>carbon</i>	<i>E-glass</i>					
<i>T</i>	[°C]	50	25	50	75	24	<i>r.t.</i>	<i>Tg-15</i>			
<i>Tg matrix</i>	[°C]	102	–	–	–	–	18	73	135	–	
<i>IFFS</i>	[MPa]	39	38	51	43	30	43	39	56	68	58
l_c/d_f	–	35	42	40	47	67	–	–	–	–	39

References	[23] Etcheverry	[31] Fraser	[24] Leonard				
<i>Matrix</i>	–	<i>PP</i>	<i>PP</i>	<i>HDPE</i>	<i>Nylon 6</i>	<i>poly(vinyl butyral)</i>	
<i>Fiber</i>	–	<i>E-glass</i>	<i>E-glass</i>	<i>E-glass</i>	<i>E-glass</i>	<i>E-glass</i>	
<i>T</i>	[°C]	<i>r.t.</i>	25	25	25	75	<i>r.t.</i>
<i>Tg matrix</i>	[°C]	–	–	–	–	–	–
<i>IFFS</i>	[MPa]	7	8	14	34	27	46
l_c/d_f	–	205	–	–	–	–	–

Table 3: Comparing IFFS (measured by fragmentation) and critical aspect ratio to other systems

IFFS have also been measured via droplet debonding tests. Debonding forces versus embedded length are shown in Fig. 7 and Tab. 4 summarizes the different specimen process conditions. Post observations reveal an adhesive failure for all studied samples and so allow us to compare obtained values (Fig. 8)

Figure 7: Debonding forces versus embedded length for all studied samples

		TP1-ASF	TP1-MSF	TP2-ASF	TP2-MSF	TS-ASF	TS-MSF
<i>System</i>	–	<i>acrylic</i>	<i>acrylic</i>	<i>acrylic</i>	<i>acrylic</i>	<i>epoxy</i>	<i>epoxy</i>
<i>Paraffin wax</i>	–	<i>No</i>	<i>No</i>	<i>Yes</i>	<i>Yes</i>	<i>No</i>	<i>No</i>
<i>Cure 1</i>	[h–°C]	–	–	1 – 80	1 – 80	1 – 80	1 – 80
<i>Cure 2</i>	[h–°C]	1 – 80	1 – 80	2 – 150	2 – 150	2 – 160	2 – 160
<i>Sample size</i>	–	21	23	18	20	12	12
IFFS	[MPa]	8.5 ± 2.4	7.8 ± 2.1	27.3 ± 4.2	27.2 ± 4.1	44.5 ± 5.1	48.8 ± 6.8

Table 4: IFFS (measured by microbond test) depending on sample type and process conditions

Figure 8: Failure modes for microdroplet samples (right TS-MSF, left TP2-ASF)

As anticipated, process and cure conditions significantly impact IFFS values. In the absence of paraffin wax, radical polymerization could not occur at high temperature because of rapid MMA evaporation. Hence TP1 samples were not fully polymerized due to the formation of a crust as the result of solvent loss. These samples exhibiting poor IFFS values are then not relevant. Using paraffin wax drastically reduces the monomer evaporation. As a consequence, polymerization time can be reduced by curing specimens at higher temperature. A higher IFFS value is then obtained for TP2 and is attributed to a full droplet polymerization and a better chemical/physical adhesion with the fiber. With these optimized conditions, it can be noted that both type of sizing lead to close interfacial adhesion which confirms fragmentation tests conclusions. However, IFFS values for acrylic matrices stay much lower than the one obtained for epoxy-based systems.

Few studies about the use of paraffin wax for that kind of system have been reported and mainly of them discuss about its role in preventing evaporation [19]. Even if it is commonly used for such an application, the effect of wax on matrix mechanical properties and/or the interfacial adhesion is still unknown. Alkane chains which constitute wax could migrate at the matrix/fiber interface and affects the properties of the latter.

Moreover, paraffin wax does not fully prevent from solvent evaporation and considering the large surface which is offered by a microdroplet, monomer loss could be much higher than expected. As a consequence, the reactive formulation compositions might be modified. Wax can also act as a plasticizer.

For all these reasons, it has to be kept in mind that interfacial behaviour of a microdroplet specimen could be not fully relevant of final composite parts.

Interfacial adhesion characteristics of related TS and TP-systems are reported Tab. 5 (sizing or fibers surface are optimized, but the polymer matrix is not modified with coupling agents) [13, 26-29]. In case of a good adhesion for TS/GF specimens, values around 50 MPa are expected, as we found for epoxies. In the case of acrylic matrices, much lower values are measured. However, our own system exhibits a better interfacial adhesion if compared to interfaces generated either by an acrylic latex coalescence [29] or by hot-melting of PP droplets [27]. This confirmed the benefits brought by a reactive approach to improve fiber/TP matrix strength.

	Zinck [13]	Kang [26]	Bénéthuilère [28]	Yang [27]	Beguinel [29]
Matrix	– epoxy	epoxy	vinylester	PP	acrylic
Fiber	– E-glass	carbon	E-glass	E-glass	E-glass
IFFS [MPa]	65– 89	≈ 55	≈ 45	10– 25	≈ 20

Table 5: Confronting acrylic IFFS values (measured by microbond test) to other systems

5 CONCLUSION

Acrylic/glass interfaces have been studied by two micromechanical approaches: the single fiber fragmentation test and the microbond test. Specimens have been prepared by polymerizing an acrylic-based reactive formulation onto glass fibers. Matrix and fiber mechanical properties have been studied and samples processing conditions optimized in order to establish relevant test conditions for each method. IFFS values measured via fragmentation tests are quite high. They compete with values reported on optimized TS-based systems and are much higher than those reported for TP/GF specimens obtained by hot pressing. In addition no significant difference in IFSS can be noted whether multi-compatible-sized or acrylic-sized fibers are involved. Microdroplet debonding analyses confirm the previous observations but larger IFFS discrepancies were measured between TS reference and acrylic-based samples. If compared to TP/glass interfaces generated from an acrylic latex evaporation or from a molten PP, a better adhesion is measured when Elium formulation is used. It demonstrates the suitability of a “reactive” strategy to process TP-based composites with improved matrix/fiber interfaces.

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REFERENCES

- [1] Y. Yang, R. Boom., D-J. van Heerden, P. Kuiper and H. de Wit, Recycling of composite materials, *Chemical Engineering and Processing: Process Intensification*, **51**, 2012, pp. 53–68 ([doi:10.1016/j.cep.2011.09.007](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cep.2011.09.007)).
- [2] I.Y. Chang and J.K. Lees, Recent Development in Thermoplastic Composites: A Review of Matrix Systems and Processing Methods, *Journal of Thermoplastic Composite Materials*, **1**, 1988, pp. 277–296 ([doi: 10.1177/089270578800100305](https://doi.org/10.1177/089270578800100305)).
- [3] K. Van Rijswijk and H.E.N. Bersee, Reactive processing of textile fiber-reinforced thermoplastic composites – An overview, *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, **38**, 2007, pp. 666–681 ([doi:10.1016/j.compositesa.2006.05.007](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compositesa.2006.05.007)).
- [4] A. Kelly and W.R. Tyson, Tensile properties of fibre-reinforced metals: Copper/tungsten and copper/molybdenum, *Journal of the Mechanics and Physics of Solids*, **13**, 1965, pp. 329-350 ([doi:10.1016/0022-5096\(65\)90035-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/0022-5096(65)90035-9)).
- [5] H.L. Cox, The elasticity and strength of paper and other fibrous materials, *British Journal of Applied Physics*, **3**, 1952, pp. 72-79 ([doi:10.1088/0508-3443/3/3/302](https://doi.org/10.1088/0508-3443/3/3/302)).
- [6] M.R. Piggott, A theory of fibre strengthening, *Acta Metallurgica*, **14**, 1966, pp. 1429–1436 ([doi:10.1016/0001-6160\(66\)90163-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/0001-6160(66)90163-5)).

- [7] T.H. Lacroix, B. Tilmans, R. Keunings, M. Desaeger and I. Verpoest, Modelling of critical fibre length and interfacial debonding in the fragmentation testing of polymer composites, *Composites science and Technology*, **43**, 1992, pp. 666–681 ([doi:10.1016/0266-3538\(92\)90061-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/0266-3538(92)90061-7))
- [8] S.F. Zhandarov and E.V. Pisarova, The local bond strength and its determination by fragmentation and pull-out test, *Composites Science and Technology*, **57**, 1997, pp. 957–964 ([doi:10.1016/S0266-3538\(97\)00037-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0266-3538(97)00037-7))
- [9] M.R. Piggott, Expressions governing stress-strain curves in short fibre reinforced polymers, *Journal of Materials Science*, **13**, 1978, pp. 1429–1436 ([doi:10.1007/BF00548734](https://doi.org/10.1007/BF00548734)).
- [10] D. Tripathi and F.R. Jones, Single fibre fragmentation test for assessing adhesion in fibre reinforced composites, *Journal of Materials Science*, **33**, 1998, pp. 1-16 ([doi:10.1023/A:1004351606897](https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1004351606897))
- [11] B. Miller, P. Muri and L. Rebenfeld, A microbond method for determination of the shear strength of a fiber/resin interface, *Composites Science and Technology*, **28**, 1987, pp. 17-32 ([doi:10.1016/0266-3538\(87\)90059-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/0266-3538(87)90059-5))
- [12] M.R. Piggott, Debonding and friction at fibre-polymer interfaces. I: Criteria for failure and sliding, *Composites Science and Technology*, **30**, 1987, pp. 295-306 ([doi:10.1016/0266-3538\(87\)90017-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/0266-3538(87)90017-0))
- [13] P. Zinck, H.D. Wagner, L. Salmon and J.F. Gerard, Are microcomposites realistic models of the fibre/matrix interface? I. Micromechanical modelling, *Polymer*, **42**, 2001, pp. 5401-5413 ([doi:10.1016/S0032-3861\(00\)00870-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0032-3861(00)00870-3))
- [14] W. Weibull, A statistical distribution function of wide applicability, *Journal of applied mechanics*, **18**, 1951, pp. 293-297
- [15] H.D. Wagner, S.L. Phoenix and P.B. Schwartz, A Study of Statistical Variability in the Strength of Single Aramid, *Journal of Composite Materials*, **18**, 1984, pp. 312-338 ([doi: 10.1177/002199838401800402](https://doi.org/10.1177/002199838401800402))
- [16] EL. M. Asloun, J.B Donnet, G. Guilpain, M. Nardin and J. Schultz, On the estimation of the tensile strength of carbon fibres at short length, *Journal of Materials Science*, **24**, 1989, pp. 3504-3510 ([doi: 10.1007/BF02385732](https://doi.org/10.1007/BF02385732))
- [17] C. Ahlstrom and J.F. Gerard, The adhesion of elastomer-coated glass fibers to an epoxy matrix. Part I: The effect of the surface treatments on the tensile strength of the glass fibers, *Polymer Composites*, **16**, 1995, pp. 305-312 ([doi:10.1002/pc.750160407](https://doi.org/10.1002/pc.750160407))
- [18] P. Zinck, M.F. Pays, R. Rezakhanlou and J.F. Gerard, Mechanical characterisation of glass fibres as an indirect analysis of the effect of surface treatment, *Journal of Materials Science*, **34**, 1999, pp. 2121-2133 ([doi: 10.1023/A:1004572112470](https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1004572112470))
- [19] S.H. Schroeter, D.A. Bolon, K.K. Webb and J.E Moore, Evaporation control of monomers from solventless resin compositions, *Radiation Physics and Chemistry*, **14**, 1979, pp. 869-882, ([doi:10.1016/0146-5724\(79\)90123-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/0146-5724(79)90123-7))
- [20] J.V. Mullin, V.F. Mazzio and R.L. Mehan, Basic failure mechanisms in advanced composites, *NASw-2093*, NASA, 1971
- [21] A.T. DiBenedetto, Measurement of the thermomechanical stability of interphases by the embedded single fiber test, *Composites Science and Technology*, **42**, 1991, pp. 103-123 ([doi:10.1016/0266-3538\(91\)90014-G](https://doi.org/10.1016/0266-3538(91)90014-G))
- [22] X.F. Zhou, H.D. Wagner and S.R. Nutt, Interfacial properties of polymer composites measured by push-out and fragmentation tests, *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, **32**, 2001, pp. 1543-1551 ([doi:10.1016/S1359-835X\(01\)00018-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1359-835X(01)00018-5))
- [23] M. Etcheverry, M.L. Ferreira, N.J. Capiati, A. Pegoretti and S.E. Barbosa, Strengthening of polypropylene–glass fiber interface by direct metallocenic polymerization of propylene onto the fibers, *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, **39**, 2008, pp. 1915-1923 ([doi:10.1016/j.compositesa.2008.09.018](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compositesa.2008.09.018))

- [24] G.C Leonard, D. Hosseinpour and J.C Berg, Modulus-Graded Interphase Modifiers in E-Glass Fiber/Thermoplastic Composites, *Journal of Adhesion Science and Technology*, **23**, 2009, pp. 2031-2046 ([doi:10.1163/016942409X12526743387809](https://doi.org/10.1163/016942409X12526743387809))
- [25] V. Rao and L.T. Drzal, The Temperature Dependence of Interfacial Shear Strength for Various Polymeric Matrices Reinforced with Carbon Fibers, *The Journal of Adhesion*, **37**, 1992, pp. 83-95 ([doi: 10.1080/00218469208031252](https://doi.org/10.1080/00218469208031252))
- [26] S. Kang, D. Lee and N.Choi, Fiber/epoxy interfacial shear strength measured by the microdroplet test, *Composites Science and Technology*, **69**, 2009, pp. 245-251 ([doi:10.1016/j.compscitech.2008.10.016](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compscitech.2008.10.016))
- [27] L. Yang and J. Thomason, Development and application of micromechanical techniques for characterising interfacial shear strength in fibre-thermoplastic composites, *Polymer Testing*, **31**, 2012, pp. 895-903 ([doi:10.1016/j.polymertesting.2012.07.001](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.polymertesting.2012.07.001))
- [28] T. Bénethuilière, J. Duchet-Rumeau, J.F. Gérard, E. Dubost and C. Peyre, Physico-chemistry of vinylester / glass fiber interfaces used in SMC composites, *20th International Conference on Composite Materials, Copenhagen, Denmark, July 19-24, 2015*
- [29] J. Beguinél, J.F. Gérard, F. Lortie, P. Gérard and J. Maupetit, Analysis and Improvement of Interfacial Adhesion in Continuous Fiber Reinforced Thermoplastic Composites, *20th International Conference on Composite Materials, Copenhagen, Denmark, July 19-24, 2015*
- [30] P. Zinck, De la caractérisation micromécanique du vieillissement hydrothermique des interphases polyépoxyde - fibre de verre au comportement du composite unidirectionnel. Relations entre les échelles micro et macro. *PHD dissertation, INSA Lyon, 1999*
- [31] W.A. Fraser, F.H. Ancker, A.T. Dibenedetto and B. Elbirli, Evaluation of surface treatments for fibers in composite materials, *Polymer Composites*, **4**, 1983, pp. 238-248 ([doi:10.1002/pc.750040409](https://doi.org/10.1002/pc.750040409))